

SSR	Entry	Primers sequence (5'-3')	Repeat Motif	LG	Band range
SSR6 ¹	O112G04b	F: CGAACATCTTAGGCCGAATC R: GGTTAACCTGCGGGATATTG	(TC)29	8	100-161
SSR9 ¹	O110B01	F: CCTCTTCAGTCGAGGTCTGG R: AATTTGGAAACAGAGTCGCC	(GA)20	7	162-169
SSR10 ¹	Na12C08	F: GCAAACGATTTGTTTACCCG R: CGTGTAGGGTGATCTAGATGGG	(CT)50	1	268-354
SSR 20 ¹	O112F02a	F: GGCCATTGATATGGAGATG R: CATTCTCAATGATGAATAGT	(TC)29	5	127-255
SSR22 ¹	O110B01	F: GCCTTAGATTAGATGGTCGCC R: ACTTCAGCTCCGATTTGCC	(CT)29	6	139-143
SSR23	Na12A02b	F: AGCCTTGTTGCTTTTCAACG R: AGTGAATCGATGATCTCGCC	(CT)16	6	163-167
SSR25 ¹	O110H04	F: TCACCCCTCTATATCCACCC R: CAGAATCTGCCTGAACATCG	(CT)29	7	158-217
SSR31 ²	BoGMS1042	F: ATAGTGAATAATGGAAGGCTG R: GAGAGAGGAGAGAACAGAGGA	(TC)14	1	182-194
SSR37 ³	BoGMS0726	F: GTTCCGAGGGTTGTTCTT R: CCATCAGGTTCCAGCCATAC	(AT)18	2	203-209
SSR39 ²	BoGMS0702	F: CGTAATGGTGAAGATACTCGG R: TCTAATCAAGAGCGTGTGGT	(AT)18	3	262-270
SSR42 ²	BoGMS1465	F: GAGGTGTTGGATACTGTGCT R: TGTTGTTGGTGTAGTGGTG	(GAA)8	3	284-299
SSR45 ²	BoGMS0560	F: ATGAAGAAGTGTGTTGGTGAG R: AAGATTGATGGAAGCAAGAA	(GAA)14	4	279-303
SSR47 ³	BnGMS681	F: GTCGAAGATTGTTGTCAGGT R: TTCACGAAGAACCCTAGAAA	(GT)8	4	142-144
SSR49 ²	BoGMS0949	F: CTCCTCCTCCTTTCATCTTC R: TTCGTCTCCCTTCTCTGTAA	(TC)15	5	164-204
SSR54 ²	BoGMS0354	F: CTGACAATGACCAAGATAAGG R: CACGCAACAACAACAACACTAC	(TGT)6(GTT)4	8	100-109
SSR58 ²	BoGMS1570	F: TCAAGCCAACGCTACTACA R: TGATGGGTGAACAACATAAAT	(AATA)6	9	192-193
SSR59 ²	BoGMS1467	F: ATGGCTTTGTTCTTCTTTCTT R: GACTTCAGCACGCCTTTC	(CTG)8	9	267-279
<i>B_FLC3</i> -SSR3 ⁴	AY306125	F: AGGCAAAATCTCTCGTATCTGG R: CTTCTGCTCCACCGATGAAT	(TC)11		206-208
<i>Bo_LFY</i> -SSR7 ⁴	FJ529019	F: ATTTTCTTTCGCTATGTCTGGC R: TGTGTCGTTTCCATAACTCGAC	(TC)15		182-184
<i>Bo_FT</i> -SSR9 ⁴	FJ848914	F: GAATCGGTATATTCAAGCCAGTC R: ACCCATGAACACTAAAATCCGT	(TCT)4		220-222
<i>Bo_CRY1</i> -SSR17 ⁴	AJ344565	F: TTGGGTGAATAATTTCCAAAAG R: TCTTCTCTGGTGCCCATAC	(T)15(T)13		324-334
<i>Bo_FRI</i> -GN19 ⁴	JF318402	F: AGCGGTCACAGTTTCTTGTC R: GCATTCCACGCTTGATACTTG	-		380